

PL - 12 Plenary Lecture

**HYPERSPECTRAL REFLECTANCE AS A NEW PHENOTYPING
TOOL FOR SOYBEAN BREEDING**

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Soybean (*Glycine max* [L.] Merr.) is the leading source of vegetable protein for both animal feed and human food utilization. Although originally domesticated in China, soybean has been successfully adapted to many regions of the world through plant breeding. For increasing soybean production in Europe, adaptation to specific environmental conditions such as organic farming, drought, low temperature or high latitude is required. Apart from classical phenotyping for agronomic traits and marker-assisted or genomic selection procedures, the availability of new phenotyping tools such as imaging or hyperspectral reflectance measurements are opening much broader views on breeding materials, which so far have been covered neither by phenotypic nor by genomic approaches. Various spectral reflectance indices (SRI) utilizing hyperspectral data have been developed, which can describe differences between soybean genotypes in developmental processes, biomass accumulation, nitrogen fixation, leaf water content and various other physiological features. Particular SRI are correlated to grain yield, seed protein content or time to maturity; thus, they might be implemented in indirect or high-throughput selection protocols. Other indices can be helpful in classifying genotypes into groups with particular physiological reaction based on photosynthesis, nitrogen metabolism or stress response patterns. Thus, soybean genotypes of different genetic background, maturity groups or divergent geographic origin (e.g. China vs. Europe) can be categorized based on SRI, and plant breeders can gain additional information for selection decisions in order to optimize adaptation to specific environments.

Key words: soybean breeding, field phenotyping, hyperspectral reflectance, nitrogen fixation.

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